

The influence of e-commerce adoption on the success of MSMEs in Empat Lawang Regency in the Covid-19 pandemic

Revita Desi Hertin

Faculty of Economy and Business/Jakarta Global University/Indonesia

revita@jgu.ac.id

ABSTRACT

Technological developments in today's modern era are increasing and spreading widely in society. This also has an impact on the business world in Indonesia, especially on how to purchase from conventional/direct purchases to online purchases using social media platforms and e-commerce platforms in Indonesia. This should be in line with the marketing strategy for business people in regions in Indonesia. A new marketing strategy must be carried out by business players in the industrial 4.0 era, the large number of competitors encourages all business players to provide new breakthroughs in the buying and selling process, including marketing products/services on e-commerce platforms and social media market places. Features in e-commerce such as lower prices, review features that make it easy to see product quality, and more complete product descriptions make it the right platform for buyers who want to buy goods online where activities occur more effectively and efficiently. This study aims to examine the influence of e-commerce in the progress of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Empat Lawang Regency during the Covid-19 pandemic. Using several variables, namely accessibility, price, and quality of goods, they are included in a questionnaire distributed to MSME actors in Empat Lawang Regency. The results of this study indicate that all variables in this study have a positive effect on sales at UKMK in Empat Lawang and show the importance of using new methods in sales. In future research, it is expected to be able to add several variables to see the relationship with sales using e-commerce.

ARTICLE INFO

Received : Dec. 7, 2022

Revised : Feb. 16, 2023

Accepted : Mar. 8, 2023

KEYWORDS

E Commerce, Product Quality, Sales, UMKM,

Suggested Citation (APA Style 7th Edition):

Hertin, R.D. (2023). The influence of e-commerce adoption on the success of MSMEs in Empat Lawang Regency in the Covid-19 pandemic. *International Research Journal of Science, Technology, Education, and Management*, 3(1), 91-104. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7777320>

INTRODUCTION

Technological developments in today's modern era are increasing and spreading widely in society. This technological change has also had an impact on the business world in Indonesia, especially on how to shop from conventional/direct purchases to online purchases using social media platforms and e-commerce platforms in Indonesia. Currently, people prefer to buy goods online because they are considered more efficient and save time, especially at the beginning of 2020 when there was a Covid-19 pandemic where the government issued several regulations including policies regarding places to shop and reducing physical contact that occurs in every activity. Using this platform is also easy because most people already have smartphones and internet services to access e-commerce platforms anywhere.

The use of the internet in various regions in Indonesia is the reason for the rapid development of progress in the digital buying and selling process in Indonesia. Based on internet world stats data, internet users in Indonesia reached 212.35 million in March 2021, with this number making Indonesia third with the most internet users in Asia. Apart from the internet, the widespread use of smartphones is also one of the reasons why business people have to implement e-commerce, including social media marketplaces. Electronic commerce which is part of this digital business is a process that occurs in buying and selling goods/services in society.

In addition, a new marketing strategy must also be carried out by business players in the industrial 4.0 era, the large number of competitors encourages all business actors to provide new breakthroughs in the buying and selling process, including marketing products/services on e-commerce platforms and social media market places. Features in e-commerce such as lower prices, review features that make it easy to see product quality, more complete product descriptions make this the right platform for buyers who want to buy goods online where activities occur more effectively and efficiently.

Empat Lawang Regency is a Regency which is the border between South Sumatra Province and Bengkulu Province. With the many resources available in this district, MSMEs are growing rapidly in various types of businesses from food, handicrafts, automotive, education etc. In 2020, according to data from the Office of Cooperatives, SMEs and Labor, the number of SMEs in Empat Lawang will reach 8,000 SMEs. These MSMEs also receive assistance from the government, namely in the form of development funds which are also called Assistance from the Center for Micro Enterprises (BUPM). BUPM is used both in terms of product quality development, distribution, and marketing processes. Marketing issues are also a problem that must be emphasized in the development of MSMEs in Empat Lawang. The use of technology is one of the steps that must be implemented by MSME actors. The use of the internet has now entered various areas including Empat Lawang, this is directly proportional to the use of smartphones which is now also a trend in Empat Lawang. This must be utilized by MSME actors in Indonesia to do so.

Electric Commerce (E-commerce) is a term used to describe the practice of purchasing and selling commodities via the internet or the practice of transferring goods, services, and information over information networks, particularly the internet (Turban et al., 2017). Based on Global Web Index data in digital 2019 Spotlight: E-commerce in Indonesia, the level of internet-related activity is also active in the use of e-commerce reaching 90% for both consumers and producers (Mendeley Wicaksana). This should be utilized by business people, namely MSME players in the Empat Lawang area. The hypothesis in this study is that the advantages of e-commerce such as real-time access, prices, more complete product information make this marketing strategy chosen by consumers. E-commerce for this marketing strategy also takes the form of various platforms, such as Shopee, Tokopedia, Facebook marketplace. the use of e-commerce and social media in the buying and selling process has also become a trend among the public lately, cheaper prices are one strong reason to shop online. This online buying and selling process also supports government policies to reduce interaction and physical contact in this Covid-19 condition.

In addition, the large number of MSMEs in Empat Lawang is a challenge in itself to utilize technology in marketing products and services. Competitive prices, prioritized product quality and complete product information

are the focus of this research. In the end, the purpose of this research is to see the role of the three variables above in the use of e-commerce which will later affect the sales and success of MSMEs in Empat Lawang Regency.

This study aims to examine the influence of e-commerce in the progress of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Empat Lawang Regency during the Covid-19 pandemic. Using several variables, namely product information, price, public access, and quality of goods, they are included in a questionnaire distributed to MSME actors in Empat Regency. Empat Lawang Regency is a district in the province of South Sumatra, with an area of 2,254.44 and a population of 333,622, Empat Lawang Regency is a regionally autonomous district in 2007, according to regional statistical data with a developing economy the number of MSMEs in this district is around 8,000 in 2007 2020. MSME actors make up the population of this study. This study uses a quantitative method where data is obtained by distributing questionnaires. The results of this study will later help MSMEs make improvements, of course, with the variables measured, namely Price, Product Quality, Product Information, and Public Access. This proposal consists of background, literature review, methods, and research timeline.

E-commerce and social media

E-commerce is a place to buy and sell online, where they provide various kinds of goods needed by the community. In the world of e-commerce there are two actors, namely traders who provide goods/services (sellers) and buyers/customers who make purchase transactions (buyers). In short, this model is the same as transactions in general involving sellers and buyers. Both as traders and buyers/customers, basic knowledge about how to shop and also how to pay will support making the right decisions for both traders and buyers when starting e-commerce activities (Marita, 2012: 107). Fulfillment of needs is indeed very important to deliver individuals to a life that is in harmony with their environment. In general, everyone will carry out consumption activities and like consumptive things such as shopping, especially if these needs are available online such as in e-commerce, then this can become a strong magnet for everyone to access them. Consumptive behavior is the behavior of buying and using goods that are not based on rational considerations and has a tendency to consume something that exceeds the limit where individuals are more concerned with desire factors than needs and are characterized by luxury and excess. The use of the most luxurious things that provide satisfaction and physical comfort.

This is one of the factors someone wants to shop. The application of e-commerce, especially to MSMEs, is generally used as a marketing strategy tool as well as a transaction method, especially in carrying out sales activities. Sales activity is very important because it will be the main income for business actors, whether micro, small or medium, with the existence of e-commerce, this will certainly facilitate the business process of doing business more effectively and efficiently. According to Kotler & Armstrong (2012) E-commerce is an internet network that can be accessed by someone using a computer. It may be used by someone to conduct business activities and by consumers to receive information using technical assistance. The process starts with offering information services to help consumers make a decision. E-commerce is the practice of conducting transactions for the purchase and sale of products and services via electronic devices, computer networks, the internet, or other digital technologies, according to Wong (2010). Conclusion: E-commerce (Electronic Commerce) is an activity that reshapes the interaction between sellers and customers by completing business transactions utilizing digital data processing and information and communication technology.

The phrase "social media" refers to a number of different technologies that can be used to bring individuals together in a cooperation with the purpose of exchanging information and interacting through web-based message content. As a result of the internet's ongoing development, consumers' access to the various technologies and functionalities changes frequently. Due to this, social media is now more of a catch-all term for many applications or designs. Information infrastructure, tools for creating and distributing media content, and social media are the three components of social media. Personal messages, news, opinions, and cultural items can all be included in media material. If media content exists in digital form, then people, businesses, and industries are the ones who create and use it.

Accessibility

Accessibility is a facility provided to see the extent to which market segments can be reached by business actors ((Rao & Srinivasu, 2013). Accessibility plays an important role in driving economic growth. Infrastructure development is able to stimulate entrepreneurial activity so that it will affect the rate of economic growth through competitive action (Rao & Srinivasu, 2013). Small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) are becoming the dominant players in free market competition in the age of the global economy. In this situation, the government's role is crucial for supporting SMEs, one of which is accessibility (Andrevski et al., 2016). According to Lupiyoadi (2001) location is a decision made by the company where the company must be in place and operational. Location Store (Store Location) is an aspect important in distribution channels. Placement or distribution constitutes distribution mechanism used to convey product from producer to consumer point. The location of the store is the most rely on what can see from the average number the audience that passes through each store day, and audience presentation stop by the shop. Presentation drops by and then buy as well as value purchase per sale. Concerning decisions. The choice of location has an impact broad and long towards the future small companies

Product quality

Product quality is an important factor that makes consumers. Quality is based on the consumer's actual experience of goods or services, as measured by customer requirements whether stated or not, realized or only felt, technically or subjectively, can represent moving targets in a competitive market (Fahmi Muhammad, 2016). Product quality plays an important role in building customer trust in sellers. Product quality in e-commerce at this time is a point that must be emphasized, to minimize the poor quality of this product, e-commerce has a review feature that allows customers to see for themselves what other customers think about the products/services offered. Product quality refers to a product's capacity to meet both overt and covert needs. Anything that can be supplied to a market for consideration, expertise, use, or consumption and satisfies a want or need is considered a product. The following eight criteria define quality: Performance refers to a product's operational characteristics. Features refer to a product's features. Reliability refers to the likelihood that a product will malfunction or fail. Compatibility refers to how well a product works with service capability criteria. A product's appearance, sound, and perceived output quality are all factors in (7) aesthetics. Four main ways that quality influences businesses are as follows: A. Cost and market share: Increasing quality can result in both cost savings and a larger market share. B. A company's reputation is determined by the following: C. Product Liability: The organization has ultimate responsibility for all consequences of using its goods or services.

Consumers now consider product quality in addition to brand attributes, price advantages, and other criteria when making product purchase decisions. As a result, the company must pay attention and continue to maintain the quality of the items it provides. While making purchases, buyers take into account more than just the product's quality; they are also influenced by other aspects like pricing and service quality. Thus, it is a fascinating issue to carefully consider.

Product Price

As we know that human needs are unlimited, while the natural resources are limited. This situation has occurred from the time since the existence of humans, from the barter era. So in this economic system there is what is called the medium as a medium of exchange. Price is something or value that is exchanged to obtain the desired goods or services and to be used as ownership rights, where through price the company obtains income (Fahmi Muhammad, 2016). In the process of buying and selling one of the factors that influence decision making in buying goods is the price. Comparison of prices on various e-commerce platforms make it easier for customers to compare products and services and make purchasing decisions. the sum of money that the consumer must pay in order to receive the good or service. Determine pricing targets and policies, price fixing, discount policy, credit policy, etc. as a factor that influences the volume of sales. According to their research, travel agencies may retain current customers by delivering an appealing and competitive pricing as well as by offering special offers. Price is one of the marketing

mix aspects that has the biggest impact on customer purchasing decisions. According to "Pricing Practices: Their Impacts on Consumer Behavior and Welfare," price has a significant impact on customers' buy intentions, particularly the reference price, which has the biggest impact because customers can't compare prices easily.

PREVIOUS STUDY

Title-Author(s)	Research Problem	Result and Finding
<p>Empowering small and medium enterprises through the implementation of e-commerce in the Tlogomas sub-district</p> <p>Paulus Lucky Tirma Irawan, Kistrilia Rega Prilianti, and Melany</p>	<p>Limited marketing of products and services in the Tlogomas sub-district even after the use of social media</p> <p>Lack of information regarding marketing strategies for MSMEs in the Tlogomas sub-district</p>	<p>Based on the findings, e-commerce is very helpful in the marketing and buying and selling processes of MSMEs in Tlogomas, and there is a need for e-commerce training for MSMEs in Tlogomas. It is necessary to update information related to accessibility and solutions by updating the MSME website.</p>
<p>Design and build e-commerce applications to increase MSME income</p> <p>Arif Tirtana, Adnan Zulkarnain, Bagus Kristomoyo Kristanto, Suhendra, Muhammad Azrul Hamzah</p>	<p>Lack of information regarding e-commerce applications in Malang district.</p> <p>The low income of MSMEs in Malang Regency is because the majority of the sales process is still conventional</p>	<p>The creation of an application for a source of information about e-commerce based on the type of business, product, and features to facilitate the buying and selling process between sellers and customers in Malang Regency.</p>
<p>Impact of Covid 19 on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) (a case study of UMKM comp Watesprojo Village, Kemlagi, Mojokerto)</p> <p>Khofifah Nur Ihza</p>	<p>The decline in the performance/revenue of MSMEs at Ikhwa Comp is due to Covid 19.</p> <p>Lack of emphasis on aspects of supporting MSME income during the Covid-19 period.</p>	<p>The recommendation for a survival strategy for MSMEs is to carry out the buying and selling process through e-commerce, digital marketing, adding consumer services and optimizing marketing relationships with consumers, and maintaining products and taking care of existing customer</p>
<p>Influence Of Store Location And Promotion On Purchase Interest Consumers At Jenawi Oblong Riau Distro, Pekanbaru</p> <p>Ulfa Ekawanti</p>	<p>The aim of this study is to ascertain the impact of store location and promotion on consumer buying interest at Distro Jenawi Oblong Riau Pekanbaru. The problem in this study is that the number of customers has decreased, the percentage of target achievement has decreased, and the company's sales target has not been achieved. Use of quantitative descriptive in this study using the SPSS software</p>	<p>When the coefficient of determination (R²) store location and promotion on consumer buying interest are calculated, the value of R square is calculated as 0,299 or 29,9% for the influence of store location alone on consumer buying interest and 0,278 or 27,8% for the influence of store location and promotion alone. This demonstrates that at Distro Jenawi Oblong Riau Pekanbaru, the location of the store and the offer have a 36% impact on consumer buying interest, with the remaining 64% being influenced by other factors not explored in this study.</p>

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aims to examine the influence of e-commerce in the progress of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Empat Lawang Regency during the Covid-19 pandemic. Using several variables, namely accessibility, price, and quality of goods, they are included in a questionnaire distributed to MSME actors in Empat Lawang Regency.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research variable

This research is research that will explain how the influence of e-commerce on MSME sales in Empat Lawang Regency. This research will consist of independent variables, dependent variables, and mediation. The independent variables in this study are accessibility, product prices, and product quality. While the dependent variable in this study is MSME sales with e-commerce mediation.

Research Approach

This research adheres to a deductive approach, where this research starts from a general theory and then narrows it down to a more specific hypothesis. The research method used is a survey method, which is a system for collecting information from or about people to describe, compare, or explain their knowledge, attitudes and habits. The data used in this study is primary quantitative data obtained from questionnaires that will be distributed and filled out by MSME business actors in Empat Lawang Regency.

Population and Sample

The population of this study is all 8,000 SMEs in Empat Lawang Regency, where the sample design to be used is probability sampling by means of convenience sampling. Convenience sampling is used to simplify the data collection process, due to limited time and manpower, as well as the social distancing conditions that are currently being implemented in Indonesia. The number of samples will be calculated and determined using the Slovin formula. Respondents in this study amounted to 100 MSME actors in Empat Lawang Regency.

Research Instrument Testing

The research instrument used in this study, namely a questionnaire, will be developed by first making an operational definition of each variable, then after that the dimensions or indicators of each of these variables will be determined. Then for the measurement scale to be used is the Likert scale with a value range of 1-5. The instrument test will first be carried out by distributing the instruments that have been made to 30 respondents to fill them in, then the results of the questionnaire are tested for reliability and validity using the SPSS 2021 application.

Data Retrieval Method

After making sure that the instrument to be used is reliable and valid, the next step is to collect data by distributing questionnaires to respondents, where the questionnaire will be made in two forms, namely in the Ms. Word and in the form of a Google form, so that the questionnaire is possible to be filled in by respondents online, whether distributed via e-mail, WhatsApp, or other / if conditions allow, it does not rule out the possibility of taking the questionnaire filler data directly.

Data Analysis and Processing

A descriptive analysis, a traditional assumption test, a hypothesis test, and a path analysis were then used to analyze the data. In other words, path analysis employs regression analysis to estimate the causal relationship between variables that have already been established based on theory. Path analysis is an extension of multiple regression analysis (Ghozali, 2011). The entire process of the method used in this study can be described in the chart below.

Figure 2. Research Flow

This study used a quantitative approach, where primary data was obtained through questionnaires as a research instrument. Respondents in this study were MSME actors in Empat Lawang Regency, especially those who have used e-commerce as a way of marketing their products. Of the 17,700 (3) existing population, a total sample of 100 respondents was calculated using the Slovin formula as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Information:

n : minimum number of samples

N: total population

e: percentage of accuracy due to sample error (10%) (4)

This study consists of independent variables (independent), intervening variables and dependent variables (dependent). The independent variables of this research are e-commerce and product innovation. The intervening variable is a competitive advantage. Finally, marketing performance is the dependent variable in this study. The conceptual framework of this research is as follows:

Gambar 1. Conceptual Framework

- H1: Accessibility has a positive effect on e-commerce success for MSMEs in Empat Lawang
- H2: Product prices have a positive effect on e-commerce success for MSMEs in Empat Lawang
- H3: Product quality has a positive effect on e-commerce success for MSMEs in Empat Lawang
- H4: E-commerce has a positive effect on sales to MSMEs in Empat Lawang
- H5: Accessibility has an effect on sales to MSMEs in Empat Lawang
- H5: Product quality has an effect on sales to MSMEs in Empat Lawang

From the picture of the research flowchart above, until this progress report was made, the results of the implementation of the research so far have reached stage number 7 of 9 processes, namely Data Retrieval. Data collection was carried out with two options, namely in person and online via Google form to respondents. So that new researchers can display the results of testing the research instrument, namely the pilot questionnaire test which includes validity tests and reliability tests.

Validity Test

Validity is derived from the word validity, which denotes the degree to which a measuring instrument's accuracy and accuracy in performing its measurement function (Azwar 1986). Moreover, validity is a metric that demonstrates that the variable being measured actually corresponds to the variable the researcher is trying to analyze (Cooper and Schindler, in Zulganef, 2006). Sugiharto and Sitinjak (2006) assert that validity is related to a variable measuring what ought to be measured. The level of precision of the study measuring instrument for the actual material being measured is referred to as validity in research. The purpose of a validity test is to demonstrate how well a measuring device actually captures the subject matter of the measurement. A validity test demonstrates how well the measurement tool actually captures the subject of the measurement. The validity test, according to Ghozali (2009), is used to assess a questionnaire's reliability or validity. When the survey's questions may provide light on the subject matter it will be measuring, the survey is said to be legitimate. When a test fulfills its intended measurement function or yields exact and accurate measurement results for the intended use, it is said to have high validity. A test is said to have low validity when the results are unrelated to the goal of the measurement.

The other side of the notion of validity is the aspect of measurement accuracy. A valid measuring instrument can carry out its measuring function precisely, also has high accuracy. The meaning of precision here is being able to detect small differences in the attributes it measures. In testing the validity of the questionnaire, it is divided into 2, namely factor validity and item validity. Factor validity is measured when items are arranged using more than one factor (between one factor and another in common). The validity of this factor is evaluated by comparing its factor scores, which represent the sum of its individual items, to its overall factor score (total of all factors). The correlation or support for the whole item (total score), which is calculated by connecting the item score with the total item score, indicates the validity of the item. If we employ many factors, we must first compare the item's score to each individual factor's score before comparing the item's score to the sum of all the factors (the sum of several factors).

The correlation calculation's outcomes will yield a correlation coefficient, which is used to gauge an item's level of validity and decide if it is appropriate for use or not. An item is deemed valid if it has a significant correlation with the overall score, as determined by a correlation coefficient significance test, which is typically conducted at a significance level of 0.05.

Reliability Test

The term reliability is the root of reliability. Consistency in measurement is the definition of reliability. Reliability is the idea that the tools used in research to gather data can be relied upon as a tool for data collection and are capable of revealing real facts in the field. According to Ghozali (2009), dependability is a method for evaluating a survey that serves as an indicator of a variable or construct. If one's responses to assertions on a questionnaire are constant or stable throughout time, it is considered to be dependable. The degree of stability, consistency,

predictability, and accuracy of a test is referred to as its reliability. High reliability measurements are those that can yield trustworthy results.

Reliability, according to Masri Singarimbun, is an index that indicates how trustworthy or trustworthy a measuring device is. A measuring tool is considered dependable if it is used repeatedly to assess the same symptoms and the measurement findings are largely consistent. In other words, accuracy demonstrates how consistently a measuring tool measures the same symptoms. demonstrates the degree to which the tool's measurement results can be trusted. The measurement results need to be trustworthy in the sense that they need to be stable and consistent. The uniformity of a sequence of measures or a succession of measuring tools is reliability, also known as dependability. This can take the form of measurements made using the same measuring tool that will yield the same results on subsequent tests, or for more subjective measurements, whether two raters produce scores that are comparable (inter-rater reliability). Validity and reliability are not the same thing. This means that while a reliable measure will consistently measure, it may not always measure exactly what is intended to be measured. Reliability in research refers to how well a test's measurement holds up after being used repeatedly on the same people and under the same circumstances. When studies offer similar results for the same measurements, they are regarded as dependable. If results from repeated measurements vary, it is untrustworthy.

A number known as the value of the reliability coefficient serves as an empirical indicator of high and low reliability. An rxx value close to 1 indicates high reliability. It is generally acknowledged that reliability is adequate if it is lower than 0.700.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

a. Validity test

The validity test in this study used the Pearson Product Moment correlation, by comparing the significant value with alpha (0.05). The instrument is said to be valid if the significant value is less than 0.05 (5). This test was carried out using the SPSS 22.0 application program, and produced the following research instruments:

Table 1. Questionnaire Items

VARIABLE	QUESTIONS
Accessibility	5
Product Price	5
Product quality	5
E-Commerce	5
Sales	5

b. Reliability Test

In making a measurement of an instrument, it requires consistency and accuracy (Tirtana et al., 2020). The reliability test was carried out by testing the Cronbach Alpha value. The instrument is said to be reliable if the Cronbach Alpha value is more than 0.70 (5). The results of the reliability test are presented in the following table:

Table 2. Result Reliability test

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha Based on Cronbach's Alpha		
Alpha	Standardized Items	N of Items
.854	.866	5

Based on the table above, all variables have a Cronbach Alpha value greater than 0.70, which means that all variables used in the study are reliable.

c. Demographic Profile Response

		Statistics				
		Age	Gender	SMSs type	SMEs Age	
N	Valid	100	100	100	100	
	Missing	0	0	0	0	
Mean		2.29	1.60	2.01	2.36	
Median		2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	
Std. Deviation		.574	.550	1.193	.785	

		Age			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	<25	6	6.0	6.0	6.0
	25-40	59	59.0	59.0	65.0
	>40	35	35.0	35.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

		Gender			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	MALE	43	43.0	43.0	43.0
	FEMALE	57	57.0	57.0	99.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

		MSME type			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Food & Beverages	45	45.0	45.0	45.0
	Fashion	27	27.0	27.0	72.0
	Hand Craft	16	16.0	16.0	88.0
	Furniture	7	7.0	7.0	95.0
	Electronic	4	4.0	4.0	99.0
	Service	1	1.0	1.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

		MSME Age			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	<1 Years	14	14.0	14.0	14.0
	1-3 Years	41	41.0	41.0	55.0
	3-5 Years	40	40.0	40.0	95.0
	>5 Years	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Analysed Primary data, 2022.

Source: Analysed Primary data, 2022.

Based on the data above, for male and female sex, respectively 57:43, age is dominated by 25-40 years, followed by more than 40 years, and <25 years. For the MSME type, it is dominated by Culinary, followed by fashion, hand crafts, furniture, electronics and services. For the age of MSMEs, there are 41 aged 1-3 years, followed by 3-5 years as many as 40 MSMEs, then as many as 14 who are less than a year old and followed by those who are more than 5 years.

Anova Test

Anova is a statistical analysis that looks at the variations in group means. A group or kind of treatment may be referenced here as a "group." Ronald Fisher, a statistician, developed and popularized Anova. Analysis of variance, or ANOVA, is the term. a statistical test method comparable to the t test. Anova has the advantage of allowing for the comparison of more than two groups' differences. Unlike the independent sample t test, which can only evaluate if the means of the two groups differ, To determine whether there is a mean difference between groups, the study hypothesis is tested using an analytical method called an ANOVA. The value of the F test or the ANOVA analysis's final output. The value of the F test or F count is the outcome of the ANOVA analysis. Thereafter, the value in table f will be compared to the calculated F value. It is possible to conclude that accepting H1 and rejecting H0 or that there is a significant difference in the mean across all groups if the calculated f value is greater than the f table. The outcome of this study's Anova test is shown below.

ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between People	124.102	99	1.254		

Within People	Between Items	27.623	4	6.906	37.618	.000
	Residual	72.697	396	.184		
	Total	100.320	400	.251		
Total		224.422	499	.450		

Grand Mean = 4.13

Source: Analysed Primary data, 2022

ANOVA test is used to measure the grand total of the variables (Irawan et al., 2020)

Hypothesis Test

A statistical technique for assessing hypotheses is the one-tailed test. Hypothesis testing establishes the veracity of a theory based on statistical data. A test is considered to be two-tailed if it demonstrates that the sample means differ from the population in both directions. A one-tailed test, however, is used when a sample's mean is merely greater or smaller than the population. So, when testing, the null hypothesis will be rejected if the dominant sample data falls on one side.

Correlations

		Aksesibilitas	Harga	Kualitas Produk	Ecommerce	Penjualan
Aksesibilitas	Pearson Correlation	1	.257**	.211*	.293**	.371**
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.005	.018	.002	.000
	N	100	100	100	100	100
Harga	Pearson Correlation	.257**	1	.764**	.659**	.728**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.005		.00	.000	.000
	N	100	100	100	100	100
Kualitas Produk	Pearson Correlation	.211*	.764**	1	.779**	.776**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.018	.000		.000	.000
	N	100	100	100	100	100
Ecommerce	Pearson Correlation	.293**	.659**	.779**	1	.798**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.002	.000	.000		.002
	N	100	100	100	100	100
Penjualan	Pearson Correlation	.371**	.728**	.776**	.798**	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	100	100	100	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

Source: Analysed Primary data, 2022

The 1-tailed significance is used as a benchmark to reject/accept the hypothesis. 1-tailed is used to test the directed hypothesis. The table above shows the six hypotheses with each variable having a positive correlation.

Based on the correlation table above, the correlation value for accessibility affects e-commerce, namely 0.002, indicating that there is a positive relationship and hypothesis 1 is accepted, for product prices and e-commerce has a value of 0.000, product quality and e-commerce is 0.000, accessibility has a positive effect on e-commerce, with a value of 0.000 product quality has a positive effect on e-commerce with a value of 0.000, for e-commerce to sales that is 0.002, which can be concluded that all hypotheses in this study are accepted

H1	Accessibility has a positive effect on e-commerce	Accepted
H2	Product prices have a positive effect on e-commerce	Accepted
H3	Product quality has a positive effect on e-commerce	Accepted
H4	Accessibility has a positive effect on e-commerce	Accepted
H5	Product quality has a positive effect on e-commerce	Accepted
H6	E commerce has a positive effect on e commerce	Accepted

One-Sample Test

One sample t test is an analytical method for comparing one independent variable is the t test. This method is used to determine whether a particular number of deviates significantly from the sample average or not. The right, left, and two-party tests are the three criteria for the t test as a descriptive hypothesis testing method. Left Side Test: The t table is positioned on the left side of the curve, making it a left side test. Right Side Test: Considering that the t table is positioned on the right side of the curve, this test is known as a right-side test. The t table is divided in half and positioned on the right and left, making it a two-party test.

One-Sample Test							
Test Value = 0							
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
					Lower	Upper	
Accessibility	51.000	99	.000	3.672	3.53	3.81	
Product price	64.859	99	.000	4.172	4.04	4.30	
Product Quality	71.077	99	.000	4.298	4.18	4.42	
Ecommerce	71.463	99	.000	4.246	4.13	4.36	
Sales	73.757	99	.000	4.282	4.17	4.40	

One sample test is used if there is an error variable (Farida et al., 2019). Based on the table the following data it shows that all variables are normal.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The results of this study answered what was asked in the research objectives and hypotheses about the influence of accessibility, product prices and product quality affecting the use of E-commerce and had a positive effect on sales and success of MSMEs in Empat Lawang. MSME owners can optimize and improve marketing performance by increasing the use of e-commerce and optimizing product prices, product quality and accessibility which will affect sales. The analysis carried out in this study is not perfect, further research is still needed to improve marketing performance for MSMEs in Empat Lawang. Therefore, it is hoped that there will be more researchers who are interested in analysing the same topic. Adding more factors that might affect competitive advantage and business performance may need to be done to complete the results in this study. The results of this study are then expected to provide benefits for related parties, and can encourage increased use of e-commerce and improve product quality in UMKM in Empat Lawang in order to increase competitive advantage and marketing performance. For future research, the next author can focus on how internet influence to the brand awareness and promotion for MSMEs in Empat Lawang. The researcher can focus more on how packaging, promotion, and package can impact to the sales.

REFERENCES

- Andrevski, G., Brass, D. J., & Ferrier, W. J. (2016). Alliance Portfolio Configurations and Competitive Action Frequency. *Journal of Management*, 42(4), 811–837. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206313498901>
- Arif, M. (2020). Product quality, influence of price and e-commerce on people's buying interest on UMKM. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 9(4), 104-111. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3750361>
- Fahmi Muhammad. (2016). Pengaruh harga dan kualitas produk terhadap keputusan pembelian surat kabar Tribun Medan [The influence of price and product quality on purchasing decisions of Tribun Medan newspaper]. *Jurnal Manajemen Pemasaran*, 10(1), 33-43. <https://doi.org/10.24912/jmp.v10i1.144>
- Farida, I., Studi Akuntansi, P., & Harapan Bersama Tegal, P. (2019). Faktor-faktor yang berpengaruh terhadap kinerja UMKM di Kota Tegal [Factors affecting the performance of SMEs in Tegal City]. *Jurnal Akuntansi Multiparadigma*, 10(1), 109-121. <https://doi.org/10.18202/jamal.2019.04.10011>
- Ihza Khofifah Nur. (2020). Dampak COVID-19 terhadap usaha mikro kecil dan menengah (UMKM) (Studi kasus UMKM Ikhwa Comp Desa Watesprojo, Kemlagi, Mojokerto) [The impact of COVID-19 on micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs): A case study of Ikhwa Comp MSMEs in Watesprojo Village, Kemlagi, Mojokerto]. *Jurnal Manajemen Pemasaran*, 14(2), 38-47. <https://doi.org/10.21831/jmp.v14i2.32654>
- Irawan, P.L.T., Kestrilia Rega Prilianti, & Melany. (2020). Pemberdayaan Usaha Kecil Menengah (UKM) melalui implementasi e-commerce di Kelurahan Tlogomas [Empowering small and medium enterprises (SMEs) through e-commerce implementation in Tlogomas Subdistrict]. *Jurnal SOLMA*, 9(1), 33–44. <https://doi.org/10.29405/solma.v9i1.4347>
- Rao, P. S. & Srinivasu, B. (2013). Infrastructure development and economic growth: Prospects and perspective. *Journal of Business Management & Social Sciences Research*, 2(1), 10-18. <http://www.borjournals.com>
- Rizaldi, T., Arief, H., & Purnomo, P. (2017). Pemanfaatan E-Commerce sebagai Strategi Peningkatan Pemasaran UMKM. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Pemasaran Jasa*, 10(2).
- Tirtana, A., Zulkarnain, A., Kristomoyo Kristanto, B., & Azrul Hamzah, M. (2020). Rancang Bangun Aplikasi E-Commerce Guna Meningkatkan Pendapatan UMKM [Design and development of e-commerce application to increase the revenue of SMEs]. *Jurnal Ilmiah Teknologi Informasi Asia*, 14(2), 115-126. <https://doi.org/10.32815/jitika.v14i2.343>
- Unggul, S., Prakasa, W., & Supriyo, A. (2020). Pendampingan hukum UMKM berbasis e-commerce di Desa Jarak, Kec. Wonosalam, Jombang [Legal assistance for SMEs based on e-commerce in Jarak Village, Wonosalam Subdistrict, Jombang]. *Jurnal Hukum Dan Pembangunan*, 1(1). <http://journal.um-surabaya.ac.id/index.php/HMN/article/view/224>